

**ОСОБЛИВОСТІ ТРАНСЛІТЕРАЦІЇ ВЛАСНИХ ІМЕН
(З ДОСВІДУ ПЕРЕКЛАДУ ДОКУМЕНТІВ) /
PECULIARITIES OF TRANSLITERATION OF PROPER NOUNS
(FROM THE EXPERIENCE OF TRANSLATING DOCUMENTS)**

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In the current context of globalization, as well as intensive labor and educational migration, the transliteration of proper nouns in translated documents is becoming increasingly significant. The correct rendering of names and surnames directly affects such critically important aspects as the legal accuracy of documents, the ability to unambiguously identify individuals in different countries, compliance with international and national standards, and the prevention of legal, bureaucratic, or everyday difficulties. This issue is particularly relevant for Ukrainian citizens who obtain residence permits or temporary protection abroad (especially in Moldova and Romania), study, work, or conclude contracts in other countries, apply for dual citizenship, submit documents for diploma recognition, inheritance procedures, and more. In translation practice, this leads to a major challenge: the absence of a unified national system for the transliteration of Ukrainian names into Romanian in the Republic of Moldova. In contrast, Ukraine has had an official transliteration system since 2010 (Cabinet of Ministers Resolution No. 55), used for issuing passports, with verification available

on the State Migration Service website. On the international level, the following standards are relevant: ISO 9:1997 — Cyrillic-to-Latin transliteration with diacritics, and SR 13456:2000 — a simplified version without diacritics. This study is based on the translator's practical experience working with personal documents (passports, certificates, diplomas, powers of attorney, etc.) between 2007 and 2025. It analyzes common issues in rendering iotated vowels, soft consonants, the letter “r”, sibilants, affricates, and cases where names are written without modification. Comparisons are made between the Ukrainian passport-based transliteration system (CMU 2010) and forms adapted to Romanian orthography. To address this issue in translation practice, two main approaches are used: (1) preserving the Latinized form of names and surnames as shown in the Ukrainian international passport — a legitimate and official method, especially for notarial, legal, or immigration-related translations; and (2) adapting to Romanian linguistic norms — suitable for informal, educational, and less formalized contexts, with attention to phonetics and orthography. The conclusion emphasizes that proper name transliteration is not only a technical but also a legal matter, requiring accuracy, responsibility, and knowledge of regulatory frameworks in both Ukraine and the target country. The lack of a unified Romanian transliteration system demands professional flexibility and careful case-by-case analysis from translators. The best practice remains to use the official Ukrainian document spelling, which has legal force in most situations. The research also provides general recommendations for translators: always check name spelling against the Ukrainian international passport; in case of discrepancies, consult the client, embassy, or relevant official authority; and avoid altering legitimate spellings, even if they appear unusual in Romanian. When translating for use in Romania or Moldova, be sure to consider local legal practices and translation requirements. Therefore, the chosen topic is strategic for translation professionals, particularly those working in notarial, immigration, legal, and educational domains. Accurate transliteration is not just about “correct spelling” - it is the key to legal recognition of a person, their documents, and their rights abroad.